

Systematic Review Protocol

This review has been conducted following Shamseer et al. (2015) PRISMA-P preferred reporting items when applicable to a non-medical qualitative review.

Section 1: Administrative information	
1a: Identification	A qualitative systematic review of intra-speaker variation in the human voice
1b: Update	The protocol was created on Feb 23, 2023. For this version contact the authors. The protocol information was modified on December 2023 as follows: 3a Contact information: Revised, as one author withdrew from the review group. The protocol information was modified on July 2024 as follows: 1a Identification: The title was subtly revised.
Registration	
2: Registration	There is no direct outcome relevant to human health, and therefore this review does not meet the criteria for PROSPERO registrations, so it is not registered.
Authors	
3a: Contact information	Corresponding author: Eugenia San Segundo*, eugenia.sansegundo@csic.es Other authors: Jonathan Delgado** Author Affiliations: *Phonetics Laboratory, Institute of Language, Literature and Anthropology, Spanish National Research Council **University of La Laguna, Spain
3b: Contributions	ESS is the guarantor, developed the search strategy and the methodology section. JD contributed to the development of the selection criteria, the risk of bias assessment strategy, and data extraction. Both authors will read, provide feedback and approve the final manuscript.
Amendments	
4: Documenting amendments	If we need to amend this protocol, we will give the date of each amendment, describe the change, and give the rationale in this section.
Support	
5a: Sources	Grant PID2021-124995OA-I00 funded by MICIU/AEI/ 10.13039/501100011033 and by ERDF/EU
5b: Sponsor	Grant PID2021-124995OA-I00 funded by MICIU/AEI/ 10.13039/501100011033 and by ERDF/EU

5c: Role of sponsor and/or funder The main authors have conducted the design of the project’s protocol, analysis plan, the data collection, and analysis. The funders have had no input on the interpretation or publication of the study results.

Section 2: Introduction

6: Rationale Audio deepfake detection is essential for addressing societal challenges such as differentiating real news from fake content or authenticating voice recordings in legal contexts. However, identifying whether a voice is human or AI-generated requires knowing which characteristics to examine, and the choice of voice features for this task is relatively unguided. This justifies the systematic review presented in this paper.

Objectives

7. Aim and research questions Hypothesizing that human voices exhibit more intra-speaker variation than deepfakes, the aim of this review is to summarize and analyze the published studies on the topic of intra-speaker variation in human voice. PICO elements include: defining the Problem/Patient/Population, Intervention/Indication, Comparison, and Outcome. In the following table, the PICO elements have been identified:

P (Problem or Patient or Population)	Speakers of any language
I (Intervention or indicator)	Acoustic parameters
C (Comparison)	Factors inducing voice variation
O (Outcome of interest)	Large intra-speaker variation

To this end, the proposed systematic review will answer the following questions:

1. According to the reviewed literature, which acoustic parameters show larger intra-speaker variation in real human voices?
2. What kind of factors inducing large intra-speaker variation are represented in the reviewed literature in speakers of any language, considering only measurable acoustic parameters?

Section 3: Methods

Eligibility criteria

8. Study characteristics Studies will be selected according to the criteria outlined below:

Study designs: Peer-reviewed articles in scholarly journals are included; grey literature and black or dark literature will be excluded.

Outcomes: Outcomes will be collected, analyzed and reported descriptively, and coded and synthesized through thematic analysis.

Timing: No publication date restrictions will be made.

Language: Articles written in any language understood by the authors of this review will be included: English, Spanish, German, French, Italian and Portuguese languages will be included.

Inclusion criteria:

- Acoustic measures as dependent variables

Exclusion criteria:

- Diachronic variation
 - General introductory studies
 - Exclusively computational or statistical studies
 - Perceptually or qualitative studies
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Information sources

9. Intended information sources

The following electronic databases will be searched:

- Web of Science
- Cochrane Library database (subtopic: ear, nose & throat > larynx):
<https://www.cochranelibrary.com/search>

The article repository of the following journal will be searched too: *International Journal of Speech Language and the Law (IJSLL)*:

<https://journal.equinoxpub.com/IJSLL>

Search strategy

10. Search strategy of databases

Systematic search will be conducted by following PRISMA guidelines where applicable. Literature search strategies will be developed using a combination of subject headings and Boolean operators:

(intra speaker OR intraspeaker OR intra-speaker)
OR
(within speaker OR withinspeaker OR within-speaker)
AND
(variation OR variability)
AND
(acoustic)
AND
(forensic)
AND
(identity OR disguise)
OR
(human OR machine)

Study records

11a: Data management

Covidence and Excel are used in the data management of this study. PDF copies of the articles will also be saved after the screening stage in the study selection process.

11b: Selection process	<p>The selection of eligible articles will be conducted in two stages. Both stages will be carried out by two independent researchers.</p> <p>First, the title and abstract of the search results will be screened against the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Those which meet the inclusion criteria will be moved through to the second stage of reviewing the full article.</p> <p>In the second stage, the two reviewers will evaluate each article blindly at one's own rate by assigning one of these three labels: "yes", "no" or "maybe".</p> <p>If both rate a reference with "yes", this reference will automatically be accepted for further consideration. If both rate a reference with "no", this reference will be automatically rejected. If one reviewer rates a reference with "yes" and the other with "maybe", this reference will automatically be accepted for further evaluation. If one reviewer rates a reference with "yes" and the other with "no" (as well as if one reviewer rated a reference with "maybe" and the other with "no"), this reference will move to the section "conflicts".</p> <p>The described automated process is enabled by the software Covidence. Disagreements will be resolved through discussion or, when necessary, consulting a third reviewer.</p> <p>The reasons for excluding trials will be recorded and reported.</p>
11c: Data collection process	<p>Data extraction and synthesis will follow the thematic synthesis approach. Extracted data will include descriptive characteristics of each study in an Excel spreadsheet.</p>

Data items	
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12: Data search variables	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Study information (study ID, author, journal and year of publication) - Objectives of the study - Data collection method - Study setting - Data analysis method - Dependent variable of the study: intraspeaker results (i.e. the acoustic results related to intraspeaker variation).
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Outcomes and prioritization	
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13: Primary and secondary outcomes	<p>The primary outcomes of the review will identify the acoustic parameters showing larger intra-speaker variation in real human voices.</p> <p>Secondary outcomes of the review will explore the factors provoking large intra-speaker variation.</p>
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Risk of bias individual studies	
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14: Assessment of risk of bias	<p>To facilitate the assessment of possible risk of bias for each study, the Critical Appraisal Skills Programme (CASP, 2018) will be used to summarize the quality appraisals across included studies.</p>
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Data synthesis	
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15a: Synthesis criteria	<p>Quantitative meta-analysis will be conducted only if the results of the data show a good number of studies measuring the same acoustic parameter, and addressing a common research question, as these are the prerequisites necessary for computing</p>
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15b: Summary criteria	a combined effect size across all of the studies. If the results of the data search are variable in diverse and fragmented ways, conducting meta analyses will not be possible, nor any other quantitative methodology. A narrative, qualitative summary will be provided.
15c: Additional analyses	The data will be coded and analyzed thematically.
15d: Type of summary planned	The findings of the review will be provided, along with a discussion, an assessment of the possible bias of the review, and implications for current research on what characteristics make a voice human (that can be used to distinguish human voices from deepfakes)

References:

Covidence systematic review software (2023). Veritas Health Innovation, Melbourne, Australia. Available at: www.covidence.org. Accessed: February 2023.

Critical Appraisal Skills Programme (2018). *CASP Qualitative Checklist*. [online] Available at: <https://casp-uk.net/checklists/casp-qualitative-studies-checklist.pdf> Accessed: 08/08/2024

Shamseer, L., Moher, D., Clarke, M., Ghersi, D., Liberati, A., Petticrew, M., ... & Stewart, L. A. (2015). Preferred reporting items for systematic review and meta-analysis protocols (PRISMA-P) 2015: elaboration and explanation. *BMJ* 2015;349:g7647.